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Research Highlights

Deciphering the Anti-cancer Mechanistic of Phytometabolites of *Nigella sativa*

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Abstract

Current cancer therapeutic interventions offer resistance, which leads to the inclination of research towards combinational therapeutic interventions, wherein multiple key targets can be aimed to achieve superior therapeutic outcomes with reduced drug resistance. *Nigella sativa*, belongs to the Ranunculaceae family and has been widely explored for its anticancer properties. This study aims to screen phytometabolites responsible for the *N. sativa* anti-cancer potential using a search engine such as Science Direct and PubMed. Further, through bioinformatic webservers like Swiss Target Prediction, GeneCard, and ShinyGO underlying mechanisms of action of these screened phytometabolites against oral cancer were elucidated. From search engines, screened phytometabolites responsible for anti-cancer activity of *N. sativa* include thymoquinone, trans-anethol, and carvacrol belonging to the terpene class, nigellone belonging to the terpenoid class, α -hederin belonging to saponin class, and nigellideine belonging to the alkaloids. Using a bioinformatics webserver, the mechanistic involved in anti-cancer potential against oral cancer of screened phytometabolites of *N. sativa* was majorly related to ER, AR, RTK family member, and its downstream signalling pathway (RAS-RAF-MEK pathway, PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathway, and JAK-STAT pathway), Wnt signalling pathway, Notch signalling pathway, Bax/Bcl2, and CDK. However, *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and clinical experimentation can validate this *in-silico* anti-cancer potential against oral cancer of screened phytometabolites of *N. sativa*.

1.1. Introduction

Cancer is considered as second cause of mortality worldwide following cardiovascular disease. Asia is estimated to have a large proportion of global cancer cases, with approximately 49% of all new cancer cases and 56.1% of cancer deaths globally in 2022. According to the Indian Medical Council research, the national cancer registry programme report 2022, 8.08 lakh cancer mortalities occur. The top five states, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal, Bihar, and Tamil Nadu, show about 45 % of the total cancer mortality (Figure. 1a) [1]. Among the five states, Uttar Pradesh showed the highest cancer death. Parallely, as per the Tata Memorial Centre Population-Based Cancer Registry (PBCR) Report, oral, gall bladder, and lung were the leading cancer sites among males of Uttar Pradesh (Figure. 1b). Whereas, breast, gall bladder, and cervix were the leading cancer

sites among females of Uttar Pradesh (Figure. 1c) [2].

Current cancer therapeutic interventions offer resistance, which leads to the inclination of research towards combinational therapeutic interventions, wherein multiple key targets can be aimed to achieve superior therapeutic outcomes with reduced drug resistance [3]. As compared to mono-therapeutic intervention, this combinational therapeutic intervention will accelerate efficacy and reduce adverse drug reactions through synergism. This combinational therapeutic intervention can be multiple semi-synthesized or synthesized lab small molecules or natural products involving a standardized enriched fraction containing multiple phyto-metabolites[4-8].

Figure 1. Cancer statistics (a) India (particularly Uttar Pradesh), (b) Prevalence in males of Uttar Pradesh, and (c) Prevalence in females of Uttar Pradesh.

N. sativa, belongs to the Ranunculaceae family and has been widely explored for its anticancer properties [9–13]. The *N. sativa* anti-cancer properties are primarily attributed to its diverse phytometabolites, including terpenes, terpenoids, saponins, and alkaloids. These phytometabolite compound includes thymoquinone, trans-anethol, and carvacrol belonging to the terpene class, nigellone belonging to the terpenoid class, α -hederin belonging to saponin class, and nigellideine belonging to the alkaloids class [14–17]. Thymoquinone activates tumor suppressor p53, leading to programmed cell death in cancer cells, halts cell division by interfering with cyclin-dependent kinases and inhibits angiogenesis that is necessary for cancerous growth. α -hederin activates caspase-3, caspase-9, and modulates AMPK/mTOR pathway

against breast cancer and colorectal cancer, respectively [18–20]. Whereas carvacrol targets major key cancerous pathways such as PI3K/AKT/mTOR, MAPK, STAT3, and Notch. In a similar fashion, nigellone and nigellideine induce apoptosis, leading to cancerous cell death. The structure of phytometabolites responsible for the *N. sativa* anti-cancer potential is demonstrated in Figure 2.

Present study aims to screen phytometabolites responsible for the *N. sativa* anti-cancer potential using a search engine such as Science Direct and PubMed. Further, through bioinformatic webservers like Swiss Target Prediction, GeneCard, and ShinyGO underlying mechanisms of action of these screened phytometabolites against oral cancer were elucidated.

Figure 2. Structure of phytometabolites attributed to the *N. sativa* anti-cancer potential.

1.2. Materials and Methods

1.2.1. Screening anticancer phyto-metabolites of *N. sativa*

N. sativa anti-cancer potential was screened from various search engines such as Science Direct, PubMed, and Google Scholar, by using keywords like ‘anti-cancer’, ‘carcinoma’, ‘*N.*

sativa’; and ‘Phyto-metabolites’. Different combinations of keywords like ‘anti-cancer and *N. sativa*’; ‘carcinoma and *N. Sativa*’; ‘anti-cancer, phytometabolites and *N. Sativa*’; and ‘carcinoma, phytometabolites and *N. Sativa*’ were pursued. Research articles that were published in the last 10 years were screened

according to relevance to the topic (involving phyto-metabolites attributed to *N. sativa* anti-cancer potential). Duplicate research articles were excluded. Cross-references and review articles were also perused to assess additional information.

1.2.2. Compound-target prediction

Screened phyto-metabolites' SMILES were obtained from PubChem. For target prediction of screened phyto-metabolites, Swiss target prediction

(<http://www.swisstargetprediction.ch/>) was used. Targets showing green bar selected for further analysis. The green bar shows the probability of a target being the target for a query phyto-metabolite. The longer the length of the green bar, the greater is the probability of the target being the target for query phyto-metabolites [21–23].

1.2.3. Diseases-target prediction

Disease targets for oral cancer were obtained from GeneCards (<https://www.genecards.org/>). The phyto-metabolite targets from Swiss target prediction were matched with the disease targets from GeneCard, and the overlapping targets were selected for further analysis.

1.2.4. Protein-protein interaction

Search Tool for the Retrieval of Interacting Genes/Proteins (STRING) (<https://string-db.org/>) web server employed to construct target-target interactions between these overlapping targets. The confidence level for analysis was set at 0.9 [24]. Targets with no interaction were excluded, and the resultant

interacted network was further analyzed for KEGG pathways.

1.2.5. Mechanistic pathway

To understand the underlying mechanism, the KEGG pathway of the resultant interacted network of targets was analyzed by ShinyGO (<http://bioinformatics.sdstate.edu/go/>) [25].

1.3. Results and Discussion

1.3.1. Screening anticancer phyto-metabolites of *N. sativa*

The *N. sativa* anticancer properties are primarily attributed to its diverse phyto-metabolites, including terpenes, terpenoids, saponins, and alkaloids. These phyto-metabolite compound includes thymoquinone, trans-anethol, and carvacrol belonging to the terpene class, nigellone belonging to the terpenoid class, α -hederin belonging to the saponin class, and nigellidine belonging to the alkaloid class. Thymoquinone activates tumor suppressor p53, leading to programmed cell death in cancer cells, halts cell division by interfering with cyclin-dependent kinases, and inhibits angiogenesis that is necessary for cancerous growth. α -hederin activates caspase-3, caspase-9, and modulates AMPK/mTOR pathway against breast cancer and colorectal cancer, respectively. Whereas carvacrol targets major key cancerous pathways such as PI3K/AKT/mTOR, MAPK, STAT3, and Notch. In a similar fashion, nigellone and nigellideine induce apoptosis, leading to cancerous cell death.

1.3.2. Compound-target prediction

Targets for the screened phyto-metabolites are shown in Figure 3. Uniprot ID of the predicted target was saved for further analysis.

P53350	Q13946	P17948	P07858
P10070	P33261	P09619	P49682
P08151	O00206	P10721	Q14289
P09917	P15538	P52732	P25103
P11511	P19099	P48039	P49354
P17706	P23975	P55072	P45983
P27338	P10636	P34913	P48067
P43681	Q14416	Q9NRA0	P53779
P08173	P18405	Q9NYA1	P41594
P08912	Q04206	O60346	P07384
P08172	P16083	Q13418	P23946
P11229	Q16678	P25774	Q9Y233
P20309	P04798	P50281	Q06124
P00918	P35869	P32297	Q12809
P00915	P03372	P49841	O76083
P22303	Q9H4B7	Q07343	P08253
P36544	P13726	O75116	Q02127
P04278	Q92831	P51677	Q9Y5Y9
P35610	P40763	P21964	P15056
P23458	P80365	Q05513	Q02224
O60674	P25105	P05093	P20393
P17252	Q07817	Q99720	P24863
O14965	P51449	P06401	P05362
Q01959	P60568	O75469	P19320
P14679	P08913	P08185	P16581
P36888	P18825	P07148	P22460
P21918	P18089	P08235	O00408
P35462	P21728	P04150	O95271
Q9BY41	P14416	Q14994	P15311
P28845	P25100	P37058	Q9H3N8
P14902	P28223	P30304	Q9GZT9
P50406	P35348	O00519	P36897
P62508	P10635	P35228	Q13639
P29475	P28222	P51681	P15121
P29474	P05023	Q99572	O96020
Q9UBN7	P18031	Q92731	Q8WWL7
P22748	P36873	Q12884	P21917
P10275	Q15172	PODMS8	Q13464
P02768	P14780	P08908	P30926
P23219	P31749	P07711	P49336
O75762	P49354	P14867	P49356
P41595	P07949	P31644	P49356
P35218	Q8NER1	P35368	P17787
P05177	P49286	P31213	P31644
P35354	P11309	Q9UHC9	P18507
Q13509	O75116	P43235	P14635
P28472	P06276	Q13315	O95067
P00390	Q9UIQ6	P25024	P24941
P21397	P35372	O43614	P24864
P15559	P41143	O43613	P06493

Figure 4. Overlapping targets of phytometabolites with GeneCard oral cancer targets.

1.3.4. Protein-protein interaction

With a confidence level of 0.9, targets with zero or one interaction were omitted. The

protein-protein interaction of the 200 targets and enriched 110 interacted targets are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively.

Figure 5. Protein-protein interaction of the 200 overlapping targets.

Figure 6. Protein-protein interaction of the enriched 110 interacted targets.

1.3.5. Mechanistic pathway

Lollipop plot of top ten KEGG pathways involving targets is represented in Figure 7. From 110 targets, 31 targets were identified in KEGG pathways of cancer (Figure 8). These 31 genes were related to ER, AR, RTK family members,

and their downstream signalling pathway (RAS-RAF-MEK pathway, PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathway, and JAK-STAT pathway), Wnt signalling pathway, Notch signalling pathway, Bax/Bcl2, and CDK.

Figure 7. KEGG dot plot of the enriched 110 interacted targets.

Figure 8. KEGG mechanistic targets for oral cancer of screened phytometabolites of *N. sativa*.

1.4. Conclusion

From search engines, screened phytometabolites responsible for *N. sativa* anti-cancer activity include thymoquinone, trans-anethol, carvacrol belonging to the terpene class, nigellone belonging to the terpenoid class, α -hederin belonging to the saponin, and nigellideine belonging to the alkaloid. Using a bioinformatics webserver, the mechanistic pathway involved in anti-cancer potential against oral cancer of screened phytometabolites of *N. sativa* was

majorly related to ER, AR, RTK family member, and its downstream signalling pathway (RAS-RAF-MEK pathway, PI3K-AKT-mTOR pathway, and JAK-STAT pathway), Wnt signalling pathway, Notch signalling pathway, Bax/Bcl2, and CDK [26,27,36–42,28–35].

However, *in vitro*, *in vivo*, and clinical experimentation can validate this *in-silico* anti-cancer potential against oral cancer of screened phytometabolites of *N. sativa*.

Ethical Approval

Not Applicable

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest concerning the research, authorship, and publication of this article.

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